

Elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini kushlanish bo'yicha genetik algoritm yordamida optimallashtirish

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Dolzarbliigi: Zamonaviy murakkab elektr tarmoqlarining ruxsat etilgan ish holatlarini aniqlash va ular orasidan optimalini tanlab joriy etish dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi. Hozirgi davrda rivojlangan davlatlarda genetik algoritmlardan foydalanish va real xususiyatlarni hisobga olgan holda yoqilg'i sarfini kamayishi ta'minlanganligi aniqlangan. Bu boradi, jumladan elektr tarmoqlarining barqarorlashgan holatlarini hisoblash va optimallashtirishda genetik algoritmlardan foydalanishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Bugungi kunda energetika sohasida yuzaga keladigan turli muammolar uchun juda ko'p optimallashtirish usullari ma'lum. Elektr energetikasi sohasini rivojlantirishning hozirgi bosqichi ajratilgan resurslarga sezilarli cheklovlar sharoitida ulardan foydalanishga bo'lgan talablarning ortishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Bu esa yangi optimallashtirish texnologiyalarini ishlab chiqish va joriy etishni dolzarbligini ko'rsatadi.

Maqsad: Elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini tugun kushlanishlari bo'yicha genetik algoritmdan foydalanib optimallashtirish maslasining matematik modellari va usullarini tahlil qilish va asoslash.

Usullar: Elektr tarmoqlarining barqarorlashgan holatlarini hisoblash va optimallashtirish nazariyasi, chiziqli va nochiziqli dasturlash, sun'iy intellekt usullari, genetik algoritmlar, tizimli tahlil usullaridan foydalanilgan.

Natijalar: Elektr tarmoqlari holatini optimallashtirishda genetik algoritmlardan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatlari tadqiq qilingan. Qo'llanilgan genetik algoritm boshqa an'anaviy optimallashtirish usullariga nisbatan tezroq va ishonchliroq natija beradi. Genetik algoritm yordamida elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini optimallashtirishda energiya samaradorligini oshirish va tizim barqarorligini ta'minlash uchun samarali vosita sifatida tavsiya etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: elektr tarmoqlari, genetik algoritm, sun'iy intellekt, optimal boshqarish, reaktiv quvvat, tugun kushlanishlari, tarmoq holatini hisoblash.

Оптимизация режимов электрических сетей по напряжению с помощью генетического алгоритма

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Актуальность: Определение допустимых режимов современных сложных электрических сетей и выбор среди них оптимального для внедрения является одной из актуальных задач. В настоящее время в развитых странах отмечено, что использование генетических алгоритмов с учётом реальных особенностей обеспечивает снижение расхода топлива. В частности, особое внимание уделяется применению генетических алгоритмов для расчёта и оптимизации устойчивых состояний электрических сетей. Сегодня в энергетической отрасли существует множество методов оптимизации для решения различных задач. Современный этап развития электроэнергетики характеризуется значительными ограничениями по выделенным ресурсам и растущими требованиями к их использованию. Это подчёркивает актуальность разработки и внедрения новых технологий оптимизации.

Цель: Анализ и обоснование математических моделей и методов решения задачи оптимизации состояний электрических сетей по напряжениям узлов с использованием генетического алгоритма.

Методы: Использованы теория расчёта и оптимизации устойчивых состояний электрических сетей, линейное и нелинейное программирование, методы искусственного интеллекта, генетические алгоритмы, системный анализ.

Результаты: Исследованы возможности эффективного использования генетических алгоритмов при оптимизации состояний электрических сетей. Применённый генетический алгоритм показывает более быструю и надёжную работу по сравнению с традиционными методами оптимизации. Генетический алгоритм рекомендован как эффективный инструмент для повышения энергоэффективности и обеспечения устойчивости системы при оптимизации состояний электрических сетей.

Ключевые слова: электрические сети, генетический алгоритм, искусственный интеллект, оптимальное управление, реактивная мощность, напряжения узлов, расчёт состояния сети.

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Optimization of power network states by voltage using genetic algorithm

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Relevance: Determining the permissible operating states of modern complex electric networks and selecting the optimal one for implementation is one of the pressing issues. Currently, in developed countries, it has been established that the use of genetic algorithms, taking into account real characteristics, ensures a reduction in fuel consumption. In particular, special attention is given to the use of genetic algorithms for calculating and optimizing stable states of electric networks. Today, numerous optimization methods are known for solving various problems in the energy sector. The current stage of electric power development is characterized by significant limitations on allocated resources and increasing demands for their efficient use. This highlights the urgency of developing and implementing new optimization technologies.

Aim: To analyze and substantiate mathematical models and methods for the problem of optimizing the states of electric networks based on node voltages using genetic algorithms.

Methods: Theories of calculation and optimization of steady states of electric networks, linear and nonlinear programming, artificial intelligence methods, genetic algorithms, and system analysis methods were used.

Results: The possibilities of effective use of genetic algorithms in optimizing the states of electric networks have been investigated. The applied genetic algorithm provides faster and more reliable results compared to traditional optimization methods. The genetic algorithm is recommended as an effective tool for increasing energy efficiency and ensuring system stability in the optimization of electric network states.

Keywords: electric networks, genetic algorithm, artificial intelligence, optimal control, reactive power, node voltages, network state calculation.

1. Kirish (Introduction)

Elektr energetika tizimlarining qisqa muddatli holatlarini rejalashtirish va operativ holatlarini boshqarishda hal etiluvchi asosiy masalalardan biri ularning tarmoqlari holatlarini optimallashtirishdir. Bunda tugunlarning rostlanuvchan reaktiv quvvatlari va kuchlanishlari hamda rostlanuvchan kontur transformatorlarining transformasiyalash koeffitsientlarini barcha texnik cheklolvar bajarilgani holda tarmoqdagi aktiv quvvat isrofini minimal bo'lishini ta'minlovchi qiymatlari topiladi. Ushbu masala umumiy holatda murakkab egri chiziqli dasturlash masalasi hisoblanadi. SHuningdek, tez-tez uning ko'p ekstremumliligi, foydalaniluvchi ma'lumotlarning ehtimolliligi, qisman noaniqligi, ba'zan funksiyalarning uzlukliligi kabi faktorlar uni yanada murakkablashtiradi.

Hozirgi davrgacha ushbu masalani echishda asosan foydalanib kelinayotgan an'anaviy usullar qatoriga chiziqli va egri chiziqli dasturlash, Lagranj, gradient kabi usullarini kiritish mumkin [1-5]. Ular o'z vaqtida mavjud hisoblash va axborot bilan ta'minlash tizimlarining imkoniyatlariga muvofiq holda progressiv sanalgan bo'lsada, elektr energetika tizimlarining taraqqiyoti, ularning murakkabligini oshishi, zamonaviy yuqori ishlab chiqarish darajasiga ega bo'lgan hisoblash va axborot-kommunikasiya tizimlarining shallanishi bilan o'zlarining nisbiy samaradorligini pasaytirib bormoqda. Hozirgi davrda ularning asosiy kamchiliklari sifatida jarayonlarning nochiziqiligi va nostasionarligini hisobga olishning qiyinligi, to'la va aniq dastlabki ma'lumotlarning talab etilishi, katta murakkab tizimlar uchun yirik masshtabli masalalarni echish tezligining pastligi, ayrim murakkab texnik cheklolvar va parametrlarning diskretligini hisobga olishning qiyinligi kabilarni keltirish mumkin. Ushbu sabablarga ko'ra elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini optimallashtirishning mavjud hisoblash va axborot-kommunikasiya texnologiyalarining imkoniyatlarini e'tiborga olgan holda zamonaviy talablarga javob beruvchi usul va algoritmlarni ishlab chiqish dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Qayd etilgan muammolarni hal etishda hozirga davrda amalga oshirilayotgan tadqiqot yo'nalishlaridan biri mazkur tipdagi masalalarni echishda sun'iy intellekt usullari asosidagi model va algoritmlarni ishlab chiqishdan iborat. Bunday model va algoritmlarni qo'llash hisobiga an'anaviy usullar uchun xarakterli bo'lgan bir qator muammolar, jumladan, ko'p ekstremumlilik, o'rganilayotgan oraliqlarda funksiyalarning uzlukliligi, foydalaniluvchi dastlabki ma'lumotlarning ehtimolliligi va qisman noaniqligi kabilarni bilan bog'liq muammolar oson hal etiladi. Hozirgi davrda ushbu sohada bir qator ishlar bajarilgan bo'lib, ular qatoriga, jumladan, [6-10] kabilarni kiritish mumkin. Mazkur ishlanmalar ularda ko'rib o'tilgan masalalarni samarali echa olish imkoniyatlariga ega bo'lsada, ularni zamonaviy talablarga javob bera oladigan mukammal universal ishlanmalar darajasiga etkazish mos takomillashtirishlarni talab etadi. Ushbu ishlarda keltirilgan usul va algoritmlarning ayrimlari aynan bir xil tipdagi masalalarni echishga moslashtirilganligi, murakkab cheklolvarni hisobga olish masalalarining ochiq qolganligi, murakkab amaliy masalalarni echish tajribalarining natijalari mavjud

emasligi bilan bog'liq ayrim kamchiliklarga ega. Ushbu sabablarga ko'ra elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini sun'iy intellekt usullari asosida optimallashtirishning samarali algoritmlarini ishlab chiqish va joriy etish muhim masala sanaladi.

Ushbu maqolada elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini rostlanuvchan tugunlarning reaktiv quvvatlari va kuchlanishlari bo'yicha genetik algoritim yordamida optimallashtirish usuli taklif etilmoqda.

2. Usullar va materiallar (Methods and materials).

Matematik model va optimallashtirish algoritmi. Elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini tugunlarning reaktiv quvvatlari va kuchlanishlari bo'yicha optimallashtirish masalasi matematik jihatdan, umumiy holatda, quyidagicha ifodalanadi:

quvvati rostlanuvchan tugunlarning reaktiv quvvatlari yoki kuchlanishlarining maqsad – elektr tarmog'idagi umumiy aktiv quvvat isrofi funksiyasi

$$\pi = \sum_{i \in \Gamma + H, \delta} P_i = \sum_{i \in \Gamma + H, \delta} \left(g_{ii} U_i^2 - U_i \sum_{j \in J_i} U_j (g_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij} + b_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij}) \right) \quad (1)$$

ning minimal qiymatini barcha tugunda aktiv quvvat balansi (balanslovchi tugundan tashqari), reaktiv quvvat balansi (balanslovchi, kuchlanishning moduli fiksatsiyalangan hamda optimal reaktiv quvvati yoki kuchlanishi topiluvchi tugunlardan tashqari) bo'yicha, balanslovchi tugunning aktiv quvvatini ruxsat etilgan minimal va maksimal chegaraviy qiymatlari bo'yicha

$$P_{\delta}^{\min} \leq P_{\delta} \leq P_{\delta}^{\max}, \quad (2)$$

optimallashtiriluvchi reaktiv quvvat va kuchlanishlarning ruxsat etilgan minimal va maksimal qiymatlari bo'yicha

$$Q_i^{\min} \leq Q_i \leq Q_i^{\max}, \quad i \in \Gamma_q, \quad (3)$$

$$U_i^{\min} \leq U_i \leq U_i^{\max}, \quad i \in \Gamma_u \quad (4)$$

chegaraviy shartlarni hisobga olib, minimal bo'lishini ta'minlovchi qiymatlarini topish talab etiladi. Bu erda G , N - generatsiyalovchi va yuklamali tugunlar to'plami; G_q , G_u – optimal reaktiv quvvati va kuchlanishi topilishi talab etilgan tugunlar to'plamlari; $\delta_{ij} = \delta_i - \delta_j$ – i - va j -tugun kuchlanishlari vektorlarining burilish burchaklari ayirmasi; g_{ii} , g_{ij} , b_{ii} , b_{ij} – xususiy va o'zaro o'tkazuvchanliklar matrisasining elementlari bo'lib, i - tugunning xususiy va uning j - tugun bilan o'zaro o'tkazuvchanliklarining aktiv va reaktiv tashkil etuvchilari.

Ko'riyatotgan masalada optimallashtiriluvchi parametrlardan tashqari har bir tugunning kuchlanishi moduli va uning burilish burchagi ham noma'lum hisoblanadi. Bunga mos holda katta murakkab elektr tarmoqlari uchun masalaning o'lchami, ya'ni uni echish natijasida topiluvchi noma'lumlar soni keskin oshadi. Ushbu jihatlarni e'tiborga olib, taklif etilayotgan usul optimallashtirish va elektr tarmog'ining barqarorlashgan holatini hisoblash masalalarini alohida echishga asoslangan. Birinchi masalasini echish natijasida optimallashtiriluvchi parametrlarning qiymatlari aniqlansa, ikkinchi masalani echish orqali barqarorlashgan holat parametrlari – barcha tugunlarning kuchlanishlari modullari va ularning vektorlarini burilish burchaklari aniqlanadi. Ko'riyatotgan masala murakkab egri chiziqli dasturlash masalasi bo'lganligi sababli ya'kuniy optimal echim ushbu masalalarni echishni iterativ tarzda yaqinlashish sharti bajarilguncha ketma-ket takrorlash asosida aniqlanadi.

Optimallashtirish masalasini echishda maqsad funksiyasi (1) chegaraviy shartlar (2)-(4) larni hisobga olib genetik algoritim yordamida minimallashtiriladi. Taklif etilayotgan ushbu usulda elektr tarmog'ining holatini tugunning reaktiv quvvati va kuchlanishi bo'yicha optimallashtirishning natijalarini bir xilligi [1, 3, 4] ni e'tiborga olib, reaktiv quvvat bo'yicha optimallashtirish tugunning kuchlanishi bo'yicha optimallashtirish bilan almashtiriladi. Bunday holatda tugunning kuchlanishi bog'langan o'zgaruvchi bo'lib qolganligi sababli chegaraviy shart (3) quyidagi ko'rinishdagi 2 ta jarima funksiyalari yordamida hisobga olinadi:

$$III_i^{\max} = \alpha e^{\beta(Q_i - Q_i^{\max})}, \quad III_i^{\min} = \alpha e^{\beta(-Q_i + Q_i^{\min})}, \quad i \in \Gamma_q. \quad (5)$$

Balanslovchi tugunning aktiv quvvatini ruxsat etilgan chegaraviy qiymatlari bo'yicha chegaraviy shart (2) ham shu tarzda hisobga olinadi.

Jarima funksiyalarida qatnashuvchi i -tugunning reaktiv quvvati va balanslovchi tugunning aktiv quvvati bo'yicha ifodalar mos tugunlar uchun quvvat balanslari ko'rinishidagi tenglamalaridan hosil qilinadi.

SHunday qilib, birinchi - optimallashtirish masalasini echishda umumlashgan maqsad funksiyasi

$$F = \sum_{i \in \Gamma + H, \delta} \left(g_{ii} U_i^2 - U_i \sum_{j \in J_i} U_j (g_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij} + b_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij}) \right) + \sum_{i \in \Gamma_q + \Gamma_u} (III_i^{\max} + III_i^{\min}) + III_{\delta}^{\max} + III_{\delta}^{\min}$$

tugunlar to'plami $G_q + G_u$ uchun (4) ko'rinishdagi chegaraviy shartlarni hisobga olib, ushbu tugunlarning kuchlanishlari bo'yicha genetik algoritim yordamida minimallashtiriladi.

Ikkinchi masalada tarmoqning normal ish holatini ifodalovchi aktiv va reaktiv quvvat balansi shaklidagi qutb koordinalarida ifodalangan tugun tenglamalari sistemasini Nyuton-Rafson usulida echish orqali elektr tarmog'ining barqarorlashgan holati hisoblanadi. Bunda to'plam $G_q + G_u$ ga kiruvchi tugunlarning kuchlanishlari o'rnida ularning optimallashtirish masalasini echishda hosil bo'lgan optimal qiymatlaridan foydalaniladi, ya'ni ushbu siklda bunday tugunlarning optimal kuchlanishlari fiksatsiyalangan tartibda qatnashadi.

1-rasmda elektr tarmog'ining holatini tugunlarning kuchlanishlari bo'yicha genetik algoritim yordamida optimallashtirish usuliga muvofiq hisoblash tartibining yiriklashtirilgan blok-xemasi keltirilgan. Unda har bir tashqi iteratsiyada genetik algoritim bo'yicha optimallashtirish hamda optimal kuchlanishlarda elektr tarmog'ining barqarorlashgan holatini hisoblash bittadan bloklar ko'rinishida tasvirlangan.

1-rasm. Elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini tugunlarning kuchlanishlari bo'yicha genetik algoritim yordamida optimallashtirish usulining yiriklashtirilgan blok-sxemasi.

Fig. 1. Generalized block diagram of the optimization method for power network states based on node voltages using genetic algorithm.

3. Natijalar va muhokama (Results and discussion)

Hisobiy-tajriba tadqiqotlarining natijalari. Elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini kuchlanish bo'yicha

3- rasm. Gradient usuli va genetik algoritm yordamda optimallashtirishda kuchlanishlarining o'zgarish jarayoni.

Fig. 3. The process of changing the strengths in optimization using the gradient method and genetic algorithm.

Shunday qilib, ko'rib o'tilgan misolda elektr tarmog'ining holatini gradient usulida optimallashtirish natijasida umumiy aktiv quvvat isrofi 0,845 MVt yoki 9,4% ga kamaysa, genetik algoritm yordamida optimallashtirish usulida 0,723 MVt yoki 8,0% ga kamayganligini ko'ramiz. Biroq, ushbu natijalarni hosil qilishda gradient usulida 14 ta iteratsiyani bajarish talab etilgan bo'lsa, genetik algoritm yordamida optimallashtirish usulida esa, 2 ta iteratsiyani bajarish talab etilgan. Bu gradient usulida iteratsiya jarayoni sekin, ayrim murakkab elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini optimallashtirishda esa, ishonchsiz ekanligini qursatadi.

Taklif etilgan elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini genetik algoritm yordamida optimallashtirish usuli maqsad funksiyasi ko'p ekstremumli, ayrim funksiyalari uzlukli, foydalaniluvchi dastlabki ma'lumotlar ehtimolli va qisman noaniq bo'lgan zamonaviy tarmoqlarning qasqa muddatli ish holatlarini rejalashtirish va opertiv holatlarini boshqarish maqsadlarida samarali foydalaniladi.

4. Xulosalar (Conclusion).

1. Elektr tarmoqlarining holatlarini tugunlarning reaktiv quvvatlari va kuchlanishlari bo'yicha genetik algoritm yordamida optimallashtirish usuli taklif etildi. U rostlanuvchan parametr bo'yicha optimallashtirish va barqarorlashgan holatni hisoblashni alohida sikllarda amalga oshirishni ko'zda tutadi.

2. Elektr tarmog'ining holatini tugunning reaktiv quvvati bo'yicha optimallashtirishni uning kuchlanishi bo'yicha optimallashtirish bilan almashtirish va bunda reaktiv quvvatning ruxsat etilgan chegaraviy qiymatlari bo'yicha cheklovlarni eksponenta ko'rinishidagi jarima funksiyasi yordamida hisobga olishga asoslangan algoritm yaratildi.

3. Elektr tarmog'ining holatini genetik algoritm yordamida taklif etilgan usulda optimallashtirish ko'p ekstremumli maqsad va uzlukli funksiyalar, dastlabki ma'lumotlar ehtimolli va qisman noaniq bo'lgan sharoitlarda masala echimini etarlicha aniqda ishonchli topish imkonini beradi.

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